

ISic0667

I.Sicily inscription 0667

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

local stone (?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

Reused in mediaeval building, SAS 3

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG75

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491376

EDCS 5000364

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1991.0900

De Vido, S. 1991. appendice: fonti letterarie, epigrafiche, numismatiche, etc.. *ASNP*. 21: 929-994. At 980

Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. *Inscriptiones Segestanae. Le iscrizioni*

greche e latine di Segesta. Pisa. At L15

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